

Orkney Science Festival 2025 Workshop Report

Protected Crop Growing in Orkney

Public Perceptions around controlled environment agriculture (CEA) including indoor/hybrid growing and vertical farming

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Image 1 – Tower Farms installation at UHI, Orkney. (photo credit Henry Creissen)

Highlights

- Workshop was held at Orkney Science Festival 2025 to gather public perceptions on indoor/hybrid growing production systems
- Participants heard about different production systems
- Participants discussed advantages and disadvantages, locations and scale of variations in CEA, such as indoor and hybrid production systems, that could be feasible in Orkney
- People perceived the potential of hybrid and indoor growing systems to provide fresher food with less food miles all year round as the main advantages
- Perceived disadvantages centred on potential for greater crop disease due to growing under cover, maintenance of the technology and having to import a nutrient solution for hydroponic systems
- There was a general consensus that vertical farming should be on a local scale with every island having its own growing facility; other potential locations included schools, colleges, hospitals and restaurants
- There was a preference for multiple, small-scale production systems rather than a single large one
- Existing facilities, such as gale-proof, hard-polycarbonate-clad versions of polytunnels (e.g. Polycrub, Polycroo, Keder), containers and garages could be used rather than purpose-built and hi-tech facilities
- Public misconceptions around indoor/vertical growing included pest and disease control, suitable crops, cost, and taste and nutrition

Future research needs

- Provide information/training about: different kinds of indoor/vertical/hybrid production systems; pest and disease control in indoor systems; taste and nutrition in produce from indoor systems
- Identify sites and locations across Orkney and outer isles suitable for indoor/hybrid growing
- Identify individuals and groups/organisations to undertake hybrid/vertical growing pilots
- Identify potential funding to support initial development of vertical growing/indoor systems
- Identify potential local markets and supply chains for vertically grown produce

1. Introduction

As part of Orkney Science Festival 2025 the opportunity arose to hold a workshop on the merits and drawbacks of different production systems. The workshop was led by Dr. Henry Creissen (UHI), Dr. Liz Dinnie and Prof. Derek Stewart (JHI), professional gardener Ed Bollom and William Benson, an innovator in vertical farming and sustainable agriculture.

Food security and resilience have increasingly become public and political concerns in recent years, with geo-political events highlighting the fragility of long supply chains and threats to global commodity trading. In addition, there are environmental concerns over how food is produced and transported, as well as human health considerations about diets and nutrition. It is therefore timely to have a discussion on the feasibility of different production systems that could be implemented in Orkney, and the potential contribution of hybrid and indoor growing systems to food security and resilience in Orkney.

The **aims** of the workshop were to:

- Introduce different production systems to a public audience
- Gather data on public perceptions around indoor/hybrid growing and vertical farming through group discussions

The workshop **objectives** were to:

- Identify the potential for increased/improved production (under cover)
- Identify research needs that James Hutton Institute and the Agronomy and Agriculture Institute could look to address for the benefit of Orkney growers

The workshop was followed by a tour of the UHI facilities, including the polytunnels, Polycrubs¹ and the newly installed Tower Farms² facility being trialled by UHI Agronomy and Agriculture Institute in a purpose-built Polycrub (see Image 1 above).

2. Production systems

In the first part of the workshop the facilitators introduced different kinds of production systems based on their background as researchers or producers.

Agriculture – Dr. Henry Creissen

Dr. Henry Creissen is the Director of the Agronomy and Agriculture Institute at the University of the Highlands and Islands at Orkney College. The Institute collaborates with farmers, growers, end-users and research organisations across Orkney and Scotland to improve the efficiency and resilience of crop production systems in the Highlands and Islands. Research activities are aimed at developing new commercial opportunities for cereals and include research on both

¹ A Polycrub is a trademarked design for a hybrid greenhouse/polytunnel designed in Shetland to resist high winds and harsh weather typical of the Orkney climate (<https://www.polycrub.co.uk/>).

² Tower Farms are a vertical, hydroponic growing system that can be fitted into small spaces (<https://www.towerfarms.com/>).

old and modern cereal varieties. Apart from creating new markets for growers and food and drink companies, the programme also aims to increase self-sufficiency in rural areas, reduce the carbon footprint of the region's food and drink industry and conserve valuable crop genetic resources.

Controlled environment agriculture – Prof. Derek Stewart

Prof. Derek Stewart is Director of The Advanced Plant Growth Centre (APGC), a Tay Cities Regional Development Deal capital project hosted at the James Hutton Institute, Invergowrie. The APGC is evolving and co-creating new technologies to investigate the potential of controlled environment agriculture to support sustainable food systems within an increasing environment of climate change. Controlling the growing environment, through monitoring of light, water, heat and humidity, allows development and optimisation of different crop traits for heat, drought and floods, and new crop varieties. Indoor and hybrid growing systems also offer the potential for new business models, shorter supply chains, reduced waste and enhanced nutrition. The APGC currently has many industry-collaborative projects on CEA.

Local Food Systems and Community Growing – Dr. Liz Dinnie

Dr. Liz Dinnie is a social researcher in the Social, Economic and Geographical Science Department of the James Hutton Institute. Her research focuses on how and why Scotland should produce more of the food that it eats – particularly fruit and vegetables. Her research has identified that local food producers and systems struggle to become established because of the lack of infrastructure to enable processing and to create viable supply chains and local food economies. Small scale producers are disadvantaged by scale and intensification of production, meaning produce is often only accessible to those who are prepared to pay a premium price for local food. Much local production is therefore undertaken by hobby growers and in community gardens by volunteers. Food growing provides many social and environmental benefits for communities and individuals however with present infrastructure there is limited potential to upscale to create viable supply chains and create genuinely local food systems that support food resilience.

Horticulture/gardening – Ed Bollom

Ed has worked as a professional gardener in historic gardens for over 20 years, including Chatsworth House, Osbourne House and Allington Castle. His passion has always been for kitchen gardens and productive gardening and he spent 5 years growing fruit, vegetables, herbs and cut flowers for King Charles at Highgrove House in Gloucestershire. During this time, he was the Senior Gardener in charge of the King's walled garden, nursery and orchards. He currently runs Bollom Gardens in north-east Scotland.

Tower Farms – William Benson

William is the founder and co-owner of Seedleaves, official resellers of Tower Garden technology catering to growers of all levels. Tower Garden is an aeroponic³ growing system which can be used for domestic and urban environments, indoors or outdoors. These self-contained systems provide small-scale growing with minimal setup and maintenance.

³ Aeroponics is a soil-less growing process in which suspended plant roots receive a nutrient solution.

3. Public perceptions of indoor and hybrid growing systems in Orkney

The second part of the workshop was small group discussions aimed at understanding public perceptions of indoor and hybrid growing systems in general. Participants were asked for their views on the advantages and disadvantages of hybrid/indoor growing systems, potential markets for produce, which people or groups would be most likely to try hybrid/indoor growing and where in Orkney such systems could be sited.

Knowledge and understanding

Participants thought that the **advantages or benefits** of indoor/hybrid growing in Orkney were around access to fresh produce, flavour and freshness of produce, nutritional value of food, reduction in food miles, savings in growing space and carbon, and improved disease/pest control, job creation. Vertical gardens might be easier for people to manage because they are no-dig and so might encourage a wider range of people to engage in some form of food growing. It was also thought that very little skill development or training would be needed to achieve a reasonably high yield and impact. Potentially a higher diversity of crops as well as increased production/yield could result from indoor growing compared with outdoor systems as the environment is more controllable which has the added benefit of extending the growing season. Participants expressed the potential social benefits of indoor growing could include greater sense of commonality and belonging for local projects as well as mental health benefits. Participants also thought that people are more likely to try eating things they wouldn't normally eat if it is something they have grown themselves leading to improved diets and health, and that produce would perhaps be more affordable and so could help to tackle food insecurity. A broader opportunity identified was that of using the islands' constrained energy as a source of power for the CEA production systems.

Potential **disadvantages or challenges** of hybrid and indoor growing included the costs and source of energy for controlled systems and whether this would lead to the construction of more wind turbines. Participants also thought that the lack of contact with the earth – the soil microbiome – was a disadvantage, alongside a lack of physical benefits and disease control. This last point seems counter-intuitive since disease control is generally thought to be a benefit of indoor and controlled production systems, reflecting the need for broader public education and information dissemination around CEA. Participants thought taste and nutrients from vertically/CEA grown crops would not be as good as traditionally grown, again highlighting a difference between public perceptions and the benefits often attributed to indoor systems by their proponents.

There was a concern that indoor growing at scale could result in multiple fields of polytunnels, which would ruin the landscape, and also that technical components and maintenance of indoor, controlled systems would mean involvement in global trade markets, possibly for parts or for expertise. This perception conflicts with other views which expressed that very little skill development or training would be necessary to achieve reasonably high yield and impact from CEA. Such views highlight the lack of public awareness and possibly understanding of CEA and also the limitations of this self-selected audience. There were concerns over the plastic that is

needed for construction, particularly of polytunnels, and the environmental impacts of using this material, alongside the costs for construction. Participants thought it unlikely that indoor systems could be classified as organic and saw this a disadvantage. This is perhaps surprising considering the improved resource use efficiency and reduced need for pesticides in indoor/hybrid systems.

Distribution, consumption and markets

Participants thought that the main **outlets/markets/supply chains** for produce from indoor and hybrid growing systems would be restaurants rather than the general population, though this may not be the case on more remote isles such as Papay (population c.60). Conversely, other groups in the workshop thought that that shops, schools, colleges and hospitals (which all need to use public procurement system) could be potential outlets for fresh produce. Hence the views on individual/community-use versus more commercial uses varied between different groups. It was expressed that if each island were to have its own growing facility then this would be able to provide food for local residents which would be especially valuable during stormy weather when boats are not able to operate.

Production and producers

When asked which **people or groups** would be most likely to try indoor/hybrid growing participants thought that hobby gardeners rather than commercial growers would be most likely to try indoor growing in Orkney, at least initially. There was a preference for keeping growing local (small scale) yet also an awareness that production at scale would be needed to feed a larger number of people or for commercial growing. The idea of growing for export was unpopular, despite the potential benefits of job creation, as this would defeat the purposes of sustainability. Participants thought that indoor/hybrid growing was best used as part of a wider growing system, perhaps alongside more conventional agriculture/horticulture as a way of extending the growing season and the range of produce grown. There were felt to be reservations about having to rely on imports of nutrient solutions for hydroponic systems.

Geography and place

In terms of **spaces and places** around Orkney that could be used for indoor/hybrid growing, participants mentioned communal and community gardens, market gardens, schools, hospitals and colleges and quarries and sheltered spots. Polycrubs and polytunnels were mentioned as suitable for indoor growing as well as shipping containers and converted garages/agricultural buildings. Participants thought that each individual island could potentially produce food as all the outer islands have Polycrubs/polytunnels and these are mostly not optimised for growing food at the moment. This rather suggests that smaller CEA/vertical/indoor growing systems may not work if the polycrubs, already widely available, are not being used for this purpose.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

From the discussions at the workshop it can be concluded that the self-selected participants who attended this workshop perceive the potential of hybrid and indoor growing systems to provide fresher food with less food miles all year round as the main advantages. Concerns centred on potential for greater crop disease due to growing under cover, maintenance of the technology and having to import a nutrient solution for hydroponic systems. Some of these concerns conflict with acknowledged outcomes and performance in CEA and highlight a need for broader socialisation and knowledge dissemination on the range and outcomes CEA have delivered to date.

There was a general consensus that vertical farming should be on a local scale (although this local scale was never defined) and that potentially each island could have its own growing facility. There was some concern that large-scale projects could take up too much space and would impact the landscape. Support for small-scale operations was further reflected by suggestions of potential locations with lots of references to schools, colleges, hospitals and restaurants. This could show that there is a preference for lots of small scale production systems rather than one larger one. This hypothesis remains to be more fully tested with the Orkney business community and this is ongoing via the Islands Deal Vertical Farming business case.

Public perceptions of CEA show that there is interest within the community to try this at a small scale, in different locations and to use public spaces adjacent to schools and hospitals where possible. However, it is unclear how aware this audience was of the public procurement process that delivers to schools and hospitals, and of the potentially significant public liability that comes with delivering to such facilities. The audience expressed support for food growing activities in Orkney that would provide some kind of food resilience and that would also provide social benefits such as a sense of belonging, physical activity and social learning. There was also a sense that existing facilities, such as Polycrubs, containers and garages could be used rather than purpose-built and hi-tech facilities. There were also public misconceptions expressed around indoor/vertical growing, such as pest and disease control, cost, and taste and nutrition.

Future research needs could include:

- Provide information/training about: different kinds of indoor/vertical/hybrid production systems; production systems management including pest and disease control, nutrient and energy inputs etc.; taste and nutrition in produce from indoor systems
- Identify sites and locations across Orkney and outer isles suitable for indoor/hybrid growing
- Identify individuals and groups/organisations to undertake hybrid/vertical growing pilots
- Identify potential funding to support initial development of vertical growing/indoor systems
- Identify potential local markets and supply chains for vertically grown produce, including public procurement
- Explore development of local production of nutrient solutions for hydro/aeroponic systems

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Image : Grapes growing in polytunnel, UHI Orkney. Credit: Liz Dinnie.